

The Impact of the Leadership Style on Organizational Culture In the Pharmaceutical Industry

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Abstract: This study examined the impact of leadership style on Organizational Culture in the Pharmaceutical Industry; this study makes use of different literature done in the past by other researchers, which enables us to gather relevant information concerning leadership styles and employee performance. Transformational leadership style was discussed during this study. The sample of this study is conducted from a pharmaceutical company in New York which is in Private sector. The sample consists of 96 individuals from different departments of the organization. The statistical package program SPSS 15.0 is used. This study found that Transformational leadership was the best form of leadership style, although some researchers have concluded that transactional leadership alone might not be the best in all situations, but a blend of both transactional and transformational leadership styles would yield better results.

Keywords: Leadership Style, Employee Performance, Transformational Leadership, Organizational Culture.

Introduction:

• Effective leadership is essential to an organization's success. It is the skill or process of persuading others to carry out duties competently, effectively, and voluntarily. A line manager can't be effective without leadership (Klein et al., 2013). The line managers' guidance turns the promise into reality. It is evident to everyone in the organization when there is strong leadership in place. Good leadership allows organizational culture to emerge naturally rather than be imposed. There is open and efficient communication. Everyone is aware of the organization's mission and vision, and they all have suggestions about how to make them better. People give their all to ensure the success of the organization because they believe they are an integral part of it. Line manager leaders are a key human resource in the organization (Sougui, 2015).

These leaders develop better people under them and the two together develop better products that can compete effectively with the products offered by the competitors. We generally think of organizations competing using their products, but today organizations probably compete more using the quality of their line manager leaders than their products (Xenikou, 2017).

- As group efforts and teamwork are essential for realizing the organizational goals, leadership becomes vital for the execution of work. Line managers have the power to positively impact those under them by modeling a cooperative and healthy attitude that is necessary for productive work. Through their excellent interpersonal skills, their leadership inspires the workforce to reach new heights of performance.
- A key component of management, leadership aids in achieving organizational objectives and maximizing efficiency. Successful management is largely dependent on successful leadership.
- A remarkable leadership behavior stresses building an environment in which every employee develops and excels.
- Line managers must have the traits of a leader. They must possess leadership qualities. With leadership qualities, line managers can develop and begin strategies that build and sustain competitive advantage.

Purpose:

In this Thesis, we intend to suggest that the most critical element currently amiss in the pharmaceutical industry is its leadership model. We will also hypothesize that an effective leadership model in the industry is the basis of shared power and management among leadership managers and colleagues, rather than direction from the top through a hierarchy of authority.

Research objective:

The objective of this research aims to achieve the following:

- The impact of the leadership styles used on the organizational culture in the US pharmaceutical companies.
- To know which leadership styles (transformational, or/and transactional) are used to change the following (technology change, change in organizational culture, change in human resources, and Job Description) in US pharmaceutical companies.
- Make appropriate recommendations in the light of the results of this study.

Research Problem:

- Study the Impact the leadership styles on the US pharmaceutical companies' development.
- Study the Impact or relations between the leadership styles used and the possible organizational culture in the US pharmaceutical companies.

Research Significant:

The Transformational leadership style, Organizational culture.

The ontology research was objectivism

The Epistemology research was positivism paradigm research.

Research paradigm and approach:

The study followed the positivism paradigm research and was descriptive. A quantitative research Deductive approach was used to analyze the hypothesized relationships.

Dependent and independent variables:

The independent variable in the study was leadership style, at the levels of (transformational and transactional); the dependent variables were organizational culture of the Pharmaceutical industry.

The concept of Leadership:

According to Armstrong Sofi, M (2015); a leader is the one in command, the one who convinces others to follow them. Though they receive a lot of attention and are positioned first in the social hierarchy, leaders ultimately require followers. Leadership is a social influence technique that optimizes other people's efforts in achieving a goal. Leadership requires others, and that implies they don't need to be "direct reports".

Leadership Styles:**2.2 The primary leadership styles are:**

- 2.2.1 Transactional Leadership Style.
- 2.2.2 Transformational Leadership Style.
- 2.2.3 Autocratic Leadership Style.
- 2.2.4 Democratic Leadership Style.
- 2.2.5 Laissez-Faire Leadership Style.
- 2.2.6 Consultative Leadership Style.
- 2.2.7 Charismatic leadership Style.

The Characteristics & Qualities of a Good Leader:

- 1- Integrity.
- 2- Ability to delegate.
- 3- Clear Communication.
- 4- Self-awareness.
- 5- Encouragement.
- 6- Stimulating work.
- 7- Influence.
- 8- Focus on team interests and needs.

Leadership in the pharmaceutical industry:

Leadership in the pharmaceutical industry: With a reputation for leadership development excellence and rigorous research, the Center for Creative Leadership (CCL®) has partnered with pharmaceutical and biotech companies for decades to foster leadership in the pharmaceutical industry and create organizational levers of change (Longe, 2014). From creative collaboration, strategy implementation, and pharmacy leadership programs to assessments and executive coaching, our global pharmaceutical leadership solutions unlock leadership potential to enable you to accelerate your strategy and results. By leadership in the Pharmaceutical industry, Longe (2015) we refer to leadership based on collaboration by all stakeholders and individuals involved in the discovery, manufacturing, approval, marketing, and sales of drugs and devices. Most discussions of leadership focus on top executives at organizations and work from the top down. They describe the personal qualities and skills of the leader as inspiring, charismatic, intelligent, strategic, decisive, sensitive, visionary, etc. These discussions mostly seem to be searching for Cyrus the Great of our generation to lead large industrial complexes and organizations. Considering that the 21st century is a different era and the pharmaceutical industry a different venture, this view of leadership is not only far from reality but outright dangerous. When everything is said and done, it is to provide high-quality, compliant, safe, and efficacious medicine in a profitable, cost-effective, and environmentally friendly manner.

The industry is becoming more complicated, and to generate efficiency through activity outsourcing and the utilization of a geographically dispersed workforce, the traditional perspective of leadership ignores these factors. It disregards the fact that all current research and evidence point to the importance of leadership that begins not with the person at the

top of a hierarchical organization but with the individuals within it and the collaborative forms of an institution that demand a different type of organization and leadership.

Leadership styles used in pharmaceutical sector:

If you look on Leadership styles from Harvard Business Review, MindTools® Club, Forbes, and many other excellent resources of Leadership Coaching in Business Management.

There is Lewin's Leadership Styles (2014), Path-Goal Theory, Transformational Leadership, Charismatic Leadership, and Blue-Ocean Leadership. Organizations have their own preferences of leadership styles they would like to see practiced by current Leaders. Most of us will understand that distributive, collaborative, and complementary leadership produces a successful pharmaceutical organization.

The four methodical quadrants of Directing, Coaching, Supporting, and Delegating can be used as a roadmap to match your leadership style and help employees advance along their professional development path. It also allows you to use a "Regressive Leadership" to bring a slipping individual performance back on track.

Transformational Leaders have integrity, they are excellent communicator, self-aware, empathic, lead with humility, take accountability, and they inspire by emotional intelligence.

A Transformational Leader can use the Situational Leadership styles effectively.

There is no "one-size fits all" leadership style for interacting with all employees and coping with all situations. Every Leader takes a different path to leadership. This is why it's useful to develop an understanding of other leadership frameworks and styles.

Types of Leader in pharmaceutical sector:

There are numerous classifications of Leaders out there. Ksenia Sizov (2023) Resources on Leadership at the Crossroads, Leadership in 21st Century. Will provide comprehensive overview on those. To determine whether a leader is transactional or transformative, authoritarian or democratic, or a mix of any of these traits, there are tests available. These sets of questionnaire may be a bit simplistic, but they can assist to point someone in the right direction on a career or organizational path.

The types of Leaders include:

1. The Strategist: leadership as a game of chess.
2. The Change-Catalyst: leadership as a turnaround activity.
3. The Transactor: leadership as deal making.
4. The Builder: leadership as an entrepreneurial activity.
5. The Innovator: leadership as creative idea generation
6. The Processor: leadership as an exercise in efficiency.
7. The Coach: leadership as a form of people development.
8. The Communicator: leadership as stage management.

A Key Performance Indicator (KPI) of your team's efficacy can be determining the kinds of Leaders you have on the team. Understanding how each of you and your coworkers can contribute most effectively on your own is helpful. As a result, there will be greater opportunities for innovative problem-solving, inclusive working, reduced stress and conflict within the team, and a culture of mutual support and trust. It also helps with future talent acquisition or succession planning preparation: what character traits and skill sets are you lacking?

What differentiates pharmaceutical companies in their relative rates of success?

What differentiates one company from the other? It refers to the number of outstanding leaders that an organization has on staff who continuously exhibit each of the key leadership skills. In today's world, leaders provide their organizations with the edge they need to become trendsetters or to differentiate them from their competitor's ever-changing pharmaceutical arena.

Ksenia Sizov (2020) the manager is a term bestowed by the organization; the leader is something you earn by modeling the behaviors. Although the opposite may not always be true, a manager can also be a leader. This also remains when evaluating leaders' achievements. I noticed 2 individuals started pharmaceutical career at the same time in 2 different companies in comparable Leadership roles. In 5 years later, one person climbed the leadership ladder on several levels while the other stayed in the same role. The key difference variables in this instance were that the more effective leader was there at the proper time and exhibited all the qualities of a good leader.

In the right role during succession planning, diversified background by transitioning across different functions and roles, worked for an organization which was flourishing and could afford to promote people, and had a great rapport with senior LT. Leaders may subconsciously keep an outer circle for everyone else and an inner circle of dependable lieutenants. So there is various complex factors interaction that would lead to progression of a Leader in an organization.

Challenges of Leadership in the Pharmaceutical Industry:

The challenges facing leaders in the pharmaceutical industry are many. The "patent cliff," shrinking R&D budgets and lackluster pipelines will likely prompt many more mergers and acquisitions and make innovation imperative (Bhargavi & Yaseen, 2016). Globalization, as well, brings with it significant challenges at multiple levels from marketing to

regulatory. Changes in technology, government policy and consumer expectations are revolutionizing relationships with key stakeholders payers, physicians and patients and impacting operations in unforeseen ways. We understand the pharmacy leadership skills required meeting these and other challenges and drive performance. We design and provide the results that you need thanks to our 50 years of research and practical experience working with thousands of pharmaceutical leaders worldwide.

Pharmacy Leadership Solutions:

Our global pharmaceutical leadership solutions accelerate business results through leadership by targeting specific areas that serve as levers of change in the organization. These solutions include:

1- What Makes a Pharmaceutical Industry Leader?

The pharmaceutical industry frequently hires academic academics and physicians (MDs), acting as a kind of farm system for the business Puni et al. (2014). Most of these scientists move into research or medical affairs roles when they join industry.

While some choose to focus only on research, others go on to become team leaders and research directors. Few make it to the top management levels of pharmaceutical companies, while others go into the commercial side of management.

2- Analysis of Pharmaceutical and Biotech Top Leadership Composite:

Potential research participants included a group of people who were recognized as successful or high-potential physician leaders by Amrop Battalia Winston or their respective companies. The following job-related behaviors described have been used to define excellent performance as a leader to help guide the identification and selection of potential study participants listed by Caliper and Amrop Battalia Winston (2016):

1. Confidently expressing ideas and opinions
2. Motivating others to perform at their best
3. Building alignment and convincing people from different functional domains.
4. Recognizing problems, issues and opportunities
5. Thinking strategically to promote growth, process improvement or in the attempt of gaining competitive advantage
6. Implementing problem-solving strategies
7. Taking action that challenges status quo
8. Willing to make tough decisions

The study participants come from a number of organizations within the pharmaceutical and biotech industries. The positions held by these individuals represent functional areas where physicians typically are employed, in the pharmaceutical and biotech industry, and included such titles as:

- Senior Director
- Executive Director
- Assistant/Associate Vice President
- Vice President
- Chief Medical Officer

3- Critical Leadership Competencies:

1- Strategic perspective. Provides an effective analysis of complicated situations and is aware of the perspective held by higher management.

2- Change management. Uses effective strategies to overcome resistance to change and support organizational change projects.

3- Leading employees. Attracts, motivates and develops employees.

4- Confronting problem employees. Takes ethical and firm action when handling troublesome employees.

5- Participative management. Involves others, listens and builds commitment.

6- Building collaborative relationships. Creates productive working connections with outside parties and colleagues.

7- Respect for differences. Values people of different backgrounds, cultures, or demographics.

8- Taking initiative. Takes charge and capitalizes on opportunities.

10- Balance between personal and work life. Balances work priorities with personal life.

11- Self-awareness. Has a clear understanding of their talents and shortcomings and an ambition to grow.

12- Career management. Provides the use of efficient career management strategies, such as methods for feedback, professional connections, and coaching.

Characteristics of a leader who is strong in leading employees:

- Delegates important tasks, not just things he/she doesn't want to do.
- Provides prompt feedback, both positive and negative.
- Pushes decision-making to the lowest appropriate level and develops employee confidence.
- Expands direct reports' possibilities for problem-solving by utilizing the knowledge base.
- When putting a change into effect, explains, responds to inquiries, and patiently listens to concerns.
- Interacts with staff in a way that develops motivation.

- Actively promotes direct reports to senior management.
- Develops employees by providing challenges and opportunities.
- creates a demanding environment to promote personal development.
- Rewards hard work and a dedication to excellence.
- Finds and attracts highly talented and productive people.

To improve employee leadership capabilities within your organization:

- Implement 360-degree leadership development assessment in order to determine the leadership gap in your own organization.
- Develop best practices, launch internal groups to share experiences and create forums to share lessons learned.
- Develop library of leadership-related material.
- Create mentorship programs for particular leaders who require assistance.

Custom Pharmaceutical Leadership Solutions:-

The critical actions that leaders must do to achieve organizational excellence:

1. One of the first steps that the leaders in the organization need to undertake is to establish why the organization exists and what it wants to achieve by David Lancefield and Christian Rangen (2021). It is the responsibility of leaders to make the organization's vision and mission clear to the people. This vision and mission effectively provides employees with an understanding of the organizational direction and allows them to clearly understand their roles and responsibilities.

2. Second step the organization's plans and policies are presented to its members by the leaders. They are to imbibe the values and the culture of the organization since these plays an important role in ensuring the achievement of the organizational goals.

3. Third step is the Leaders provide a structured approach. The action plan that best satisfies the objectives of the organization can be produced using the structured method. An inclusive planning approach also gives individuals the chance to recognize, participate in, comprehend, and accomplish clearly defined goals.

1. Leaders have an open and engaging relationship with the people. This relationship demonstrates that the people are valued as an integral part of the organization, creates a sense of ownership among people, and develops a closer alignment between individual and organizational objectives.

2. Good leadership can help the organization remain focused during a time of crisis, reminding the people of their achievements and encourage them to set short term, achievable goals.

3. Also the commitment of leaders shapes the common goals of the organization and provides inspiration and motivation for people to perform at a high level.

4. Leaders provide encouragement to people for openly contributing and discussing new ideas in a positive environment and make use of their diverse experience and ideas to improve the organization.

Line managers with effective leadership qualities exhibit (Fig 1) a combination of some of the following qualities.

The Role of Leadership in Change Management:

The most challenging task for a manager to do is to execute changes without causing major disruptions to the entire company. There will be proponents and opponents of alterations to the regular course of business. A manager should be aware of the perspectives held by both parties. Minor adjustments can occasionally be made, like a new benefits scheme. At times, however, significant adjustments are required, like relocating the business across the nation and terminating staff. You will never be able to please everyone when it comes to change, but a competent manager will foresee responses and concentrate on clear communication.

Among other traits and responsibilities of a leader, leadership decision-making (LDM) provides constant innovation and significant new insights into leadership and management activities in all organizational operations From American Management Association (2021).

- Decision making is the selection of one or more alternative actions or objects, taking into account the benefits and drawbacks of the supporting data for each.

The definition of leadership decision-making (LDM) is the dynamic process of selecting among the best available options and is linked to the systemic act of decision-making.

Major Factors that Influence Leadership Decision Making in Organizations:

The main elements influencing organizational leaders' decision-making are still being investigated in this work. Research aimed at analyzing the benefits and difficulties of sound leadership decision-making as a continuous process may prove useful in the future for achieving organizational success and objectives by Katie Shonk (2023). Numerous studies conducted by researchers from various fields have demonstrated that some significant elements might affect how leaders make decisions in organizations. People make decisions about many things differently and under different situation. For example, Professionals with responsibility for product management, manufacturing, marketing research, and financing may make decisions regarding new products. They make financial decisions, which may also involve some of the other types of decisions and judgments, as well as personal decisions, such as those related to health, relationships, and careers, as well as political ones. The technique used to make decisions is frequently somewhat

customized to the choice being made. Certain decisions are easy to understand and seem straightforward, while others are complicated and call for a multi-step process to be made.

Organizational Culture

Organizational culture is the set of values, beliefs, attitudes, procedures, and regulations that define and shape employee behavior inside an organization by Michael D. Watkins (2013). The way stakeholders, including vendors, customers, and workers, see the company and its brand is reflected in its culture.

When you watch how a manager corrects an employee who errors, how a team adjusts to new consumer needs, or how a CEO manages a crisis, you can witness business culture in action.

How important is culture to your business?

- **Improve recruitment efforts:** 77% of prospective employees take the company culture into account before applying.
- **Improve employee retention:** 65% of workers stay at their current jobs primarily because of the culture.
- **Improve brand identity:** 38% of workers say that a bad workplace culture makes them want to leave their position.
- **Increase engagement:** Positively oriented businesses have up to 72% greater employee engagement rates.

An organization's behaviors and procedures reveal its culture. For example, consider:

- **Interview process:** A company's organizational culture is reflected in how much importance it places on a candidate's cultural fit or technical proficiency.
 - **Wellness incentives:** Employers that prioritize the mental and physical well of their staff members frequently provide benefits including paid time off, discounted gym memberships, tuition reimbursement, and cheap transportation.
- It can be difficult to change an organization's culture, but once it is, staff members will start exhibiting new attitudes, behaviors, and work ethics that support the organization's objectives and core values.

There are four types of organizational culture:

1. **Clan Culture:** horizontally structured, cross-team cooperation.
2. **Adhocracy Culture:** People exchange ideas and push the business to take chances.
3. **Market Culture:** Emphasizes individual employee contribution and financial success.
4. **Hierarchical cultures:** Clear managerial procedures and career tracks are given top priority

Methodology

3.1 Hypotheses Development:

We proposed the model for developing leadership management with the following Hypotheses:

H01 There is no Impact of the Leadership Style on Organizational Culture in the Pharmaceutical Industry.

H01.1: There is no Impact of Leadership Style on long-term/short-term orientation.

H01.2: There is no Impact of Leadership Style on masculinity and femininity.

H01.3: There is no Impact of Leadership Style on individualism /collectivism.

3.1. Sample

The sample of this study is conducted from a pharmaceutical company in New York which is in Private Sector. The sample consists of 96 individuals from different departments of the organization.

3.2 Measures:

The questionnaire consisted of 3 independent sections including measurement scales is designed To assess the constructs of this study and demographic information.

Demographic Variables: In the first section of the questionnaire there are demographic variables Such as gender, age, position at job, educational background and tenure in the organization to gain general information about the respondents.

Measurement of Transformational Leadership: There are four subscales which are charisma, being the source of inspiration, and individual support; which are measured by 5 items from "strongly disagree" to "strongly agree".

Measurement of Organizational Culture: There are five subscales which are long / short term orientation, masculinity/femininity, being the member of organization and certainty. All of these subscales are measured by 5 items from "strongly disagree" to "strongly agree".

Analyzing data:

According to the descriptive statistics, the sample consists of 37 women and 59 men. 49% (47 participants) of the sample is between the ages of 20-30, 34% (33 participants) of the sample is between the ages of 31-40 and 17% (16 participants) of the sample is between the ages of 41-50 and higher than 50. 54% (52 participants) are white-collar employee, 46% (44 participants) are blue-collar employee. 4% (4 participants) are primary school graduates, 42% (40 participants) are high school graduates, 38% (33 participants) are university graduates, 16% (15 participants) have a Master's Degree. 31% (30 participants) have a tenure in the organization between 0-5 years, 52% (50 participants) have a tenure in the organization between 6-10 years, 17% (16 participants) have a tenure in the organization more than 11 years. The statistical package program SPSS 15.0 is used.

Reliability Analysis: The reliability analysis is conducted for transformational leadership and organizational culture. Cronbach alpha scores are ranged between 0.893 and 0.975. The means, standard deviations and reliability coefficients for each variable are given in Table 2.

Table A: General characteristics of the study sample individuals

Gender	Sample No.	Total	Percentage
Gender		96	100%
Women	37		
Men	59		
Age		96	100%
20-30	47		49%
31-40	33		34%
41-50 & Higher than50	16		17%
Class of employees		96	100%
white color	52		54%
black color	44		46%
Education		96	100%
Primary School	4		4%
High School	40		42%
University graduate	33		38%
Master graduate	15		16%
Experience		96	100%
0-5	30		31%
6-10	50		52%
Higher than 11	16		17%

Table1: Means, Standard Deviations and Reliability Coefficients of Transformational Leadership and Organizational Culture

Scale	Mean Std.	Dev.	Cronbach α
Transformational Leadership (overall)	3.7421	1.1845	0.8963
- Charisma	3.6791	1.0974	0.8521
- Being the source of inspiration	4.0973	1.0168	0.8873
- Being intellectual	3.5690	1.1683	0.8632
- Individual support	3.3782	1.1739	0.8792
Organizational Culture (overall)	2.5247	1.5789	0.9750
- Long / Short term orientation	3.1983	0.9832	0.8943
- Masculinity / Femininity	2.9673	1.1298	0.9453
- Individualism / Collectivism	2.7830	1.0354	0.9532

This table shows the transformational leadership style with means (3.74). Of all the transformational leadership factors, inspiration is the most frequently utilized; the potential organizational culture was challenging, as indicated by (2.5), which is less than 3.

3.3 - Testing research hypotheses

The main study hypothesis states that “there is no statistically significant effect at the level of significance ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) of leadership style on organizational culture in the pharmaceutical industry.”

The main hypothesis was divided into three sub-hypotheses, each of which deals with the effect of leadership style on each dimension of the dependent variable.

To test the main hypothesis and its branches, simple linear regression analysis was used, and the results were as follows:

Table (2): * Results of simple linear regression analysis to demonstrate the effect of leadership style on organizational culture in the pharmaceutical industry in terms of its dimensions combined and individually.

Dependent variable	Independent variable	R	R ²	R ² Adj.	Standard error of the model	F value	Sig F*	B	T value	Sig T*

long-term/short-term orientation	Leadership Style	0.551	0.303	0.301	0.111	102.217	0.000	0.702	6.324	0.000
Masculinity and femininity.		0.581	0.337	0.337	0.101	124.214	0.000	0.751	7.436	0.000
individualism /collectivism		0.510	0.260	0.261	0.091	79.154	0.000	0.624	6.857	0.000
Organizational Culture		0.613	0.375	0.380	0.112	159.214	0.000	0.841	7.509	0.000

*The effect is statistically significant at the level ($\alpha \leq 0.05$)

It is clear from Table (2) the effect of Leadership Style No Organizational culture in the Pharmaceutical Industry, as it is clear from the table that there is a statistically significant effect of leadership style on the organizational culture and its sub-dimensions, as all significance level values appeared (Sig F, Sig T) respectively less than 0.05. It is clear from the table that there are strong and positive correlations between leadership style, organizational culture and its sub-dimensions, based on the value of the correlation coefficient R, all of which appeared to be wavelike and greater than 50%. It is also clear from the table that (37.5%) of the change in organizational culture results from a change in leadership style, and (33.7%) of the change in masculinity and femininity results from a change in Leadership Style, and (30.3%) of the change in long-term/short-term orientation results from The change in Leadership Style, and that (26.0%) of the change in individualism / collectivism results from the change in Leadership Style, the main hypothesis and its branches are rejected and the alternative hypothesis is accepted, which states that:

“There is a statistically significant effect at the significance level ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) of leadership style on organizational culture in the pharmaceutical industry.”

Top U.S. Pharmaceutical industry Ranked:

The global pharmaceutical industry is expected to witness positive growth as the top pharma companies are at forefront of the fight against COVID-19.

From Johnson & Johnson to Shanghai Pharmaceuticals, Pharmaceutical Technology lists the top 3 pharmaceutical companies in 2020, based on revenues.

Top 3 of the world’s biggest pharmaceutical companies:

1. Johnson & Johnson – \$56.1bn
2. Pfizer – \$51.75bn
3. Roche – \$49.23bn

Conclusion (Evaluation):

The results of the analyses reported in this study indicate significant findings which will give information about how these concepts are interacting in American organizations and these findings will also provide a significant addition to the literature. With increase of technological advances and changes, there is need for organizations to address employee satisfaction, organizational commitment, work itself and organizational culture.

Creating an organizational culture and make it stable for a period that all of the members in the organization share the common values and norms and these can be achieved with a leader who has good communication skills, high charisma. Also, it is important to have a leader who is the source of inspiration and intellectual.

For any organization to successfully navigate the always competitive market, leadership has become a critical component. In view of that leaders in organizations are recognized as supporters of change.

It is therefore, fundamental for the leadership to always try to communicate and motivate employees in order to get acceptable outcomes that can increase workers commitment and loyalty to the organization.

Several leadership styles were reviewed in this paper: ranging from transformational leadership, laissez-faire leadership, transactional leadership, strategic leadership, to consultative and participative leadership. Additionally, a transformational leader can establish distinct performance incentives and encourage and motivate employees to balance in a clever and creative approach (as the leader is constantly acquainted with their needs).

Limitations:

The sample size is one of the study's limitations. The sample of the study consists of only one firm from production sector in pharmaceutical industry. The research could be carried out in different production and service provider sectors. The second limitation of this study is the time. If this study could be performed in wider time period the results would be different because of the changes in business environment.

Recommendations:

The purpose of this research is to define how transformative leadership behavior affects organizational culture. Further work should contain a more diverse sample from different sectors, maybe from different regions to observe the effect of cultural dimensions on the variables that are searched. Also, this study investigates transformational leadership. Transactional or authentic leadership can be analyzed in further studies.

I recommend doing a similar study to the subject of this thesis, which can study in Egypt, and explaining the extent of the positive and negative impact of use the leadership management and Organizational change and culture and its impact on the success of Pharmaceutical Industries Business in Egypt. Such as Pharco group, GNP Pharmaceutical industry and Sigma Pharmaceutical industry and the extent of its relationship to the health insurance in Egypt.

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